

The New Physical Theory of the Solar System

by Mohamed shawer

This new theory discusses the structure of the Sun as imagined by the author, the dynamics of planetary motion, and how they formed.

1- The Sun is a jet-powered star, similar to a rocket, propelled forward by the energy ejected from its propellant. This propels it forward, creating a conical vortex that attracts all the planets. One side of the Sun has significant topography, while the other side is smooth. This tilt of the conical vortex causes the four seasons.

2- The solar system originated from a collision between the Sun and another star. This collision shattered the other star, and the Sun penetrated its molten debris. The Sun's vortex attracted this debris, and over time, it sorted the debris according to its mass, forming planets and moons.

3. The dynamics of planetary motion: They revolve involuntarily within the Sun's conical vortex, and their position is determined by their mass. The greater the mass, the closer they are to the beginning of the vortex, and vice versa.

4. The author uses a compass needle to support his theory, arguing that it points northward as a counter-reaction to the Earth's movement southward behind the Sun.